

Technical Report: Formalization and Translation of Network Terms for the Synthesis of Structural Variants of Simulation Models

Jan Winkels^{1,3}, Jannik Löhn¹, Felix Özkul², Robin Sutherland², Christoph Stahl¹, Jakob Rehof^{1,3}, and Sigrid Wenzel²

¹ TU Dortmund University Chair for Software Engineering, Departement for Computer Science, Germany

{jan.winkels,jannik.loehn,christoph.stahl,jakob.rehof}@tu-dortmund.de
<http://www.se.cs.tu-dortmund.de>

² University of Kassel, Germany

{felix.oezkul,robin.sutherland,sigrid.wenzel}@uni-kassel.de
<http://www.uni-kassel.de/go/pfp>

³ Lamarr Institute for Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence, Germany
<https://lamarr-institute.org/>

1 Introduction

The design and synthesis of discrete-event simulation models for material flow systems increasingly rely on formal methods to manage structural complexity and support systematic model generation. In this report, we present the formal foundations underlying our approach to structural model synthesis using the Combinatory Logic Synthesizer with Predicates (CLSP). This framework builds on Finite Combinatory Logic with Predicates (FCLP) and enables the structured generation of model variants that adhere to well-defined constraints.

This technical report extends and complements the paper “*Synthesizing Structural Variants in Discrete-Event Simulation Models using Finite Combinatory Logic with Predicates*”, authored by the same team. While the paper focuses on the overall synthesis approach and its application in simulation modeling, the present report provides a self-contained formal treatment of the underlying definitions, consistency conditions, and translation mechanisms from synthesis terms to executable structures. Importantly, the approach is limited to generating valid structural variants of simulation models based on a fixed set of actions and domain-specific constraints. It does not create simulation models from scratch or model real systems automatically.

To support a rigorous understanding of the synthesis process, we formalize key concepts such as resources, actions, material flow graphs, and network terms. We show how network terms, as the output of the synthesis process, can be systematically translated into consistent material flow graphs via intermediate representations. This formalization provides the theoretical backbone for

the CLSP-based approach and ensures the correctness and consistency of the generated simulation model structures.

This technical report is self-contained and intended as a reference for researchers and practitioners interested in the formal semantics of synthesis processes for simulation model structures, particularly in the context of production and logistics systems. It is important to note that our approach is not designed for synthesizing arbitrary simulation models of real systems. Rather, the synthesis method targets structural variants of simulation model structures based on a predefined set of valid modeling elements. These elements must reflect domain-specific semantics and stem from an existing, validated simulation model.

2 Formalization of material flow graphs

We define material flow graphs in the context of material flow simulation models as a formal abstraction of system behavior based on resource transformations and directed interactions. To formalize the relationship of the output of our synthesis framework to these graphs, we abstract them into a simple formalism similar to directed graphs.

2.1 Preliminaries

Definition 1 (Resource). *The set \mathcal{R} of resources is a finite set of distinguishable elements.*

Definition 2 (Action). *Given two sets $R_{in}, R_{out} \subseteq \mathcal{R}$ of resources with $R_{in}, R_{out} \neq \emptyset$, an action m is a tuple (R_{in}, R_{out}) .*

Remark 1. For an action $m = (R_{in}, R_{out})$, we call $m_{in} = R_{in}$ the input and $m_{out} = R_{out}$ the output of the action.

2.2 Material flow graphs

Material flow graphs capture the relationships between actions and resources.

Definition 3 (Material flow graph). *Let \mathbb{M} be a set of actions, S an opaque set of structural nodes and $K_{in}, K_{out} \in \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R})$ the model input and output nodes.*

A material flow graph $G = (V, E)$ is a directed graph with nodes $V = \mathbb{M} \cup S \cup \{K_{in}, K_{out}\}$ and edges E .

We call \mathcal{G} the set of all material flow graphs.

Definition 4 (Material flow). *Given a material flow graph $G = (V, E)$, a material flow $F : E \rightarrow \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R}) \setminus \{\emptyset\}$ is a function that describes the resources that can be transported over each edge.*

We call the input/output of some node v $F_{in}, F_{out} : V \rightarrow \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{R})$ with

$$\begin{aligned} F_{in}(v) &= \bigcup \{F(e) \mid \exists w \in V. e = (w, v) \in E\} \\ F_{out}(v) &= \bigcup \{F(e) \mid \exists w \in V. e = (v, w) \in E\} \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2. A material flow graph $G = (V, E)$ with a corresponding material flow F may be denoted as a tuple (V, E_F) with

$$E_F = \{(e, F(e)) \mid e \in E\}$$

An element $(e, x) \in E_F$ is denoted as e_x .

Of course, in a real material flow system, it is reasonable to assume that the material flow cannot be arbitrary. To ensure that only actions transform resources and that resources are neither created nor destroyed in structural nodes, consistency is defined as follows:

Definition 5 (Consistent material flow graph). *A material flow graph $G = (V, E)$ with $V = \mathbb{M} \cup S \cup \{K_{in}, K_{out}\}$ is consistent (with material flow F), iff there exists a material flow $F : E \rightarrow \mathbb{P}(R)$ so that the following conditions hold:*

(1) *No empty edges:*

$$\forall e \in E. F(e) \neq \emptyset$$

(2) *Structural nodes preserve resources:*

$$\forall s \in S. F_{in}(s) = F_{out}(s)$$

(3) *Actions transform resources:*

$$\forall M \in \mathbb{M}. F_{in}(M) = M_{in} \wedge F_{out}(M) = M_{out}$$

(4) *G is connected*

2.3 Network Terms

Formally, the result of a CLSP synthesis is a labelled tree, with the combinator names as labels for each node with the arguments to that combinator as its children.

In our framework, we use the combinators ACTION, SEQ, PAR, LOOP and OPT:

Definition 6 (Network Term). *A network term describes a network as a term and is given by the following grammar:*

$U, D, L, R, T ::= \text{ACTION}(m) \mid \text{SEQ}(L, R) \mid \text{PAR}(U, D) \mid \text{LOOP}(T) \mid \text{OPT}_X(T)$
for each action m and each $X \subseteq \mathcal{R}$. We call \mathcal{N} the set of all network terms.

Definition 7 (Root). *Let root be the function that maps a network term T to its outer-most constructor symbol.*

$$\text{root}(C(\text{args}, \dots)) = C$$

Definition 8 (Input/Output). *A network term has an input and output behavior, that can be inductively computed by the function*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{io}(\text{ACTION}(m)) &= (m_{in}, m_{out}) & \text{io}(\text{SEQ}(L, R)) &= (L_{in}, R_{out}) \\ \text{io}(\text{PAR}(U, D)) &= (U_{in} \cup D_{in}, U_{out} \cup D_{out}) \\ \text{io}(\text{LOOP}(T)) &= (T_{in} \setminus T_{out}, T_{out} \setminus T_{in}) & \text{io}(\text{OPT}_X(T)) &= (X \cup T_{in}, X \cup T_{out}) \end{aligned}$$

Remark 3. For a given network term T , we use T_{in} and T_{out} as notation for the first and second projection of $\text{io}(T)$.

Definition 9 (Consistent Network Term). A network term T is consistent, iff, for all subterms
 $SEQ(L, R)$ of $T : L_{out} = R_{in}$ and $LOOP(U)$ of $T : U_{in} \cap U_{out} \neq \emptyset \wedge U_{in} \neq U_{out}$

This definition of consistency ensures that a material flow graph created from a consistent network term is itself consistent. This is later proven as Theorem 1:

Theorem 1. A transformation μ exists, so that if T is a consistent network term, then $\mu(T)$ is a consistent material flow graph.

Since network terms are the output of the CLS synthesis, construction of multiple terms which result in the same material flow graphs is restricted via a normal form to avoid spending unnecessary time on them during enumeration:

Definition 10 (Normal form). A network term T is in normal form, iff, for all subterms

$$SEQ(L, R) \text{ of } T : root(L) \neq SEQ \quad \text{and} \quad PAR(U, D) \text{ of } T : root(U) \neq PAR$$

In addition to the normal form, which does not reduce the set of consistent graphs created, some additional restrictions are applied to avoid “trivial” redundancies and to generate more interesting solutions:

Definition 11 (Reduced Network Term). A network term T is reduced, iff, for all subterms

$$PAR(U, D) \text{ of } T : root(U) \neq OPT \wedge root(D) \neq OPT \wedge \neg(U_{in} \subseteq D_{in} \wedge U_{out} \subseteq D_{out})$$

$$LOOP(N) \text{ of } T : root(N) \notin \{LOOP, OPT\}$$

$$OPT_X(N) \text{ of } T : root(N) \neq OPT_Y \quad \text{for all } Y \subseteq \mathcal{R}$$

2.4 Translation of network terms into material flow graphs

This section shows how network terms can be translated into material flow graphs. To that aim, another intermediate representation called a *graph expression* is introduced. This simplifies the proof of consistency (Theorem 1). It also is a nice and concise representation of material flow graphs that will be used in examples.

Definition 12 (Graph Expression). A graph expression is an intermediate representation and is given by the following grammar with start symbol E :

$$E = A \mid P \mid S \quad A = \langle m \rangle \mid E^+ \mid E_X^? \quad P = E \mid S \dots S \quad S = E \mid [P + \dots + P]$$

for each action m and each $X \subseteq \mathcal{R}$. We call \mathcal{E} the set of all graph expressions.

Similar to regular expressions, when interpreted as a material flow graph (see later definition 15), the expressions $E_1 \dots E_n$ and $[E_1 + \dots + E_n]$ mean the sequential/parallel composition of the graphs represented by E_1, \dots, E_n , the expression E^+ means the graph represented by E with an additional edge that allows looping that graph and $E_X^?$ means the graph represented by E with an additional edge (labeled X) to skip that graph.

Definition 13 (*expr*). *The function $\text{expr} : \mathcal{N} \rightarrow \mathcal{E}$ computes a graph expression from a given network term:*

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{expr}(\text{ACTION}(m)) &= \langle m \rangle & \text{expr}(\text{SEQ}(L, R)) &= \text{expr}(L) \cdot \text{expr}(R) \\
 \text{expr}(\text{PAR}(U, D)) &= [u_1 + \dots + u_n + d_1 + \dots + d_m] \text{ with} \\
 & \begin{cases} u_1 + \dots + u_n = U_1 + \dots + U_n, & \text{if } \text{expr}(U) = [U_1 + \dots + U_n] \\ u_1 = u_n = \text{expr}(U), & \text{else} \end{cases} \\
 & \begin{cases} d_1 + \dots + d_m = D_1 + \dots + D_m, & \text{if } \text{expr}(D) = [d_1 + \dots + d_m] \\ d_1 = d_m = \text{expr}(D), & \text{else} \end{cases} \\
 \text{expr}(\text{LOOP}(E)) &= E^+ & \text{expr}(\text{OPT}_X(E)) &= E_X^?
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 4. If two network terms n_1 and n_2 are in normal form and are different, then $\text{expr}(n_1) \neq \text{expr}(n_2)$. Additionally, if there exist a network term n_1 with $e = \text{expr}(n_1)$, then there also exists a network term n_2 in normal form so that $e = \text{expr}(n_2)$.

Definition 14 (**Consistent/Reduced Graph Expression**). *A graph expression e is called a consistent/reduced graph expression iff there exists a consistent/reduced network term t so that $e = \text{expr}(t)$.*

Remark 5. With *expr* now defined, the motivations for Definition 11 are now more clear. When only considering consistent network terms in normal form, the following exemplary “redundant” (graphs created from) sets of graph expressions over some other expressions E, F and $X \subseteq \mathcal{R}$ are synthesized:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \{[E + F]_X^?, [E_X^? + F], [E_X^? + F_X^?]\} & \quad \{[E + F], [E + F + F]\} & \quad \{E^+, E^{++}\} \\
 \{E_X^?, E_{XX}^?\} & \quad \{E_X^{++}, E_X^{++}\}
 \end{aligned}$$

When restricting the synthesis to only be based on reduced consistent network terms, for each of the sets above, only the first expression is constructed.

Definition 15 (*graph*). *The function $\text{graph} : \mathcal{E} \rightarrow \mathcal{G}$ computes a material flow graph from a given consistent graph expression. It is defined via a helper function δ that maps each graph expression to a 6-tuple $(V, E_F, f, l, \phi, \tau)$, with V as the set of action nodes and structural nodes, E_F as the set of edges excluding the input and output edge, f and l as the first/last node of the graph and ϕ and τ as the necessary in-flow and out-flow. For an action, just construct the action node:*

$$\delta(\langle m \rangle) = (\{m\}, \{\}, m, m, m_{in}, m_{out})$$

In a sequence add edges to combine the subgraphs. The labels match up in a correct way because the graph expression is consistent:

$$\delta(X_1 \cdot \dots \cdot X_n) = (N_1 \cup \dots \cup N_n, E_1 \cup \dots \cup E_n \cup E, f_1, l_n, \phi_1, \phi_{n+1})$$

with:

- $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}. (N_i, E_i, f_i, l_i, \phi_i, \phi_{i+1}) = \delta(X_i)$
- $E = \{(l_1, f_2)_{\phi_2}, \dots, (l_{n-1}, f_n)_{\phi_n}\}$

To place subgraphs in parallel create nodes **split** and **join** and add edges from these to/from the first/last node of the subgraphs respectively, add edges to combine the subgraphs:

$$\delta([X_1 + \dots + X_n]) = (N_1 \cup \dots \cup N_n \cup \{\text{split}, \text{join}\}, E, \text{split}, \text{join}, \bigcup_i^n \phi_i, \bigcup_i^n \tau_i)$$

with:

- Unique nodes **split** and **join**
- $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}. (N_i, E_i, s_i, l_i, \phi_i, \tau_i) = \delta(X_i)$
- $E = E_1 \cup \dots \cup E_n \cup \{(\text{split}, f_i)_{\phi_i} \mid i \in \{1, \dots, n\}\} \cup \{(l_i, \text{join})_{\tau_i} \mid i \in \{1, \dots, n\}\}$

To loop parallel subgraphs enable a loop with an edge from **join** to **split**:

$$\delta([X_1 + \dots + X_n]^+) = (N, E \cup \{(join, split)_{\phi \cap \tau}\}, \text{split}, \text{join}, \phi \setminus \tau, \tau \setminus \phi) \text{ with:}$$

$$(N, E, \text{split}, \text{join}, \phi, \tau) = \delta([X_1 + \dots + X_n])$$

To skip parallel subgraphs enable a skip with an edge from **split** to **join**:

$$\delta([X_1 + \dots + X_n]_X^?) = (N, E \cup \{(split, join)_X\}, \text{split}, \text{join}, \phi \cup X, \tau \cup X) \text{ with:}$$

$$(N, E, \text{split}, \text{join}, \phi, \tau) = \delta([X_1 + \dots + X_n])$$

To loop or skip some other term F that is not translated via one of the previous cases simply transform them into a parallel expression with only one subgraph and use the same procedure as above:

$$\delta(F^+) = \delta([F]^+) \quad \delta(F_X^?) = \delta([F]_X^?)$$

Given a consistent graph expression E with $\delta(E) = (V, E_F, f, l, \phi, \tau)$, we now have:

$$\text{graph}(E) = (V \cup \{K_{in}, K_{out}\}, E_F \cup \{(K_{in}, f)_{\phi}, (K_{out}, l)_{\tau}\})$$

To prove Theorem 1, we need some additional definitions and lemmas:

Definition 16 (Input/Output for graph expressions). The definition of input and output behavior for network terms (Definition 8) can easily be extended to graph expressions:

$$ioe(\langle m \rangle) = io(\text{ACTION}(m)) \quad ioe(E_1 \cdot \dots \cdot E_n) = (E_{1in}, E_{nout})$$

$$ioe([E_1 + \dots + E_n]) = (\bigcup_{i=1}^n E_{iin}, \bigcup_{i=1}^n E_{iout})$$

$$ioe(E^+) = (I \setminus O, O \setminus I) \text{ with } (I, O) = ioe(E)$$

$$ioe(E_X^?) = (X \cup I, X \cup O) \text{ with } (I, O) = ioe(E)$$

Remark 6. From now on, $in(E)$ and $out(E)$ are used as notation for the first and second projection of $ioe(E)$.

Lemma 1. Let E be a consistent graph expression. Then for all subterms

$$S_1 \cdot \dots \cdot S_n \text{ of } E : \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}. out(S_i) = in(S_{i+1})$$

$$F^+ \text{ of } E : in(F) \cap out(F) \neq \emptyset \wedge in(F) \neq out(F)$$

Proof. By definition, there exists a consistent network term T so that $E = \text{expr}(T)$.

Clearly, by the definition of *expr*, for E to be of the form $E_1 \cdot \dots \cdot E_n$, T has to have a binary-tree-like structure with SEQ as intermediate nodes and network terms $\{T_i \mid E_i = \text{expr}(T_i)\}$ as the leaves.

Lemma 2. *Let E be a consistent graph expression. Then the in-flow and out-flow computed by δ in Definition 15 are equal to $\text{in}(E)$ and $\text{out}(E)$ respectively.*

Proof. A direct comparison of Definition 15 and Definition 16 reveals a completely analogous construction. The proof is then a simple proof by structural induction.

Lemma 3. *Let X be a consistent graph expression and Y be a sub-expression of X . Let $G = (V, E)$ and F be the material flow graph and material flow computed by $\text{graph}(X)$. With δ from Definition 15, let $\delta(Y) = (_, _, f, l, \phi, \tau)$.*

Then:

$$F_{\text{in}}(f) = \bigcup \{F((a, f)) \mid \exists a \in V. (a, f) \in E\} = \phi$$

$$F_{\text{out}}(l) = \bigcup \{F((l, a)) \mid \exists a \in V. (l, a) \in E\} = \tau$$

Proof. Let Y be any expression not of the form $[A_1 + \dots + A_n]$. Then f and l are not structural nodes *split* or *join*. Then, in E , there is only a single incoming edge to f with flow ϕ and only a single outgoing edge from l with flow τ . This can be seen directly in Definition 15.

Now, let f and l be *split* and *join* respectively. If in X there is a sub-expression $A = Y^+$, an additional edge $e = (f, l)_{\phi \cap \tau}$ is constructed. However, in $\delta(A)$, ϕ and τ are “updated” to $\phi' = \phi \setminus \tau$ and $\tau' = \tau \setminus \phi$. By induction of this lemma, the union of all labels of further incoming edges to f is ϕ' and the union of all labels of further outgoing edges from l is τ' . Together with the additional edge e with flow $\phi \cap \tau$, there is:

$$\phi' \cup (\phi \cap \tau) = \phi \setminus \tau \cup (\phi \cap \tau) = \phi \qquad \tau' \cup (\phi \cap \tau) = \tau \setminus \phi \cup (\phi \cap \tau) = \tau$$

Lemma 4. *Let $G = (V, E)$ be a material flow graph and F a corresponding material flow. If conditions (2) from Definition 5 holds, but condition (5) does not, then G has a cycle that consists only of structural nodes and the label of each edge in that cycle shares at least one resource r .*

Proof. Let G be such a material flow graph.

Because condition (5) does not hold, there exists an edge $e = (v, w)$ and a resource $r \in F(e)$ so that there is no path between an input/output/action node x and another input/output/action node y that includes r in all labels and includes e .

Trivially, v and w must be structural nodes. Because of condition (2), there must be nodes v', w' and edges $a = (v', v), b = (w, w')$ with $r \in F(a)$ and $r \in F(b)$. Also, v' and w' can obviously only be structural nodes.

By repeating this thought, the final source of r must be w and the final sink of r must be v . Therefore a cycle of structural nodes exists.

Now we can prove Theorem 1:

Theorem 1. *A transformation μ exists, so that if T is a consistent network term, then $\mu(T)$ is a consistent material flow graph.*

Proof. Let $\mu(T) = \text{graph}(\text{expr}(T))$. Let T be a consistent network term. Then, by definition, $X = \text{expr}(T)$ is a consistent graph expression. Let $G = (V, E)$ be the material flow graph and F be the material flow computed by $\text{graph}(E)$. Now we prove the conditions for $\text{graph}(E)$ to be a consistent material flow graph in the same order as in Definition 5:

(1) *No empty edges*

Recall the helper function δ from Definition 15. Each label assigned to an edge is either constructed in an inductive call, taken from an action M (but M_{in} and M_{out} are non-empty by definition), constructed as a union of other labels (then it can not be empty unless the other labels are) or constructed when handling a loop. Recall:

$$\delta([X_1 + \dots + X_n]^+) = (N, E \cup \{(join, split)_{\phi \cap \tau}\}, f, l, \phi \setminus \tau, \tau \setminus \phi) \text{ with:}$$

$$(N, E, f, l, \phi, \tau) = \delta([X_1 + \dots + X_n])$$

Because Lemma 2, $\phi = in([X_1 + \dots + X_n])$ and $\tau = out([X_1 + \dots + X_n])$. Because of Lemma 1, $in([X_1 + \dots + X_n]) \cap out([X_1 + \dots + X_n]) \neq \emptyset$. Therefore, the label assigned to the new edge is non-empty.

(2) *Structural nodes preserve resources*

The only structural nodes created by δ are *split* and *join*. Recall:

$$\delta([X_1 + \dots + X_n]) = (N_1 \cup \dots \cup N_n \cup \{split, join\}, E, split, join, \bigcup_i^n \phi_i, \bigcup_i^n \tau_i)$$

with:

- Unique nodes **split** and **join**
- $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}. (N_i, E_i, s_i, l_i, \phi_i, \tau_i) = \delta(X_i)$
- $E = E_1 \cup \dots \cup E_n \cup \{(split, f_i)_{\phi_i} \mid i \in \{1, \dots, n\}\} \cup \{(l_i, join)_{\tau_i} \mid i \in \{1, \dots, n\}\}$

By Lemma 3, we have $F_{in}(split) = \bigcup_i^n \phi_i$ and $F_{out}(join) = \bigcup_i^n \tau_i$.

The only other incoming edges to *split* are $\{(split, f_i)_{\phi_i} \mid i \in \{1, \dots, n\}\}$ and the only other outgoing edges from *join* are $\{(l_i, join)_{\tau_i} \mid i \in \{1, \dots, n\}\}$.

Therefore:

$$F_{out}(split) = \bigcup_i^n \phi_i = F_{in}(split)$$

$$F_{out}(join) = \bigcup_i^n \tau_i = F_{in}(join)$$

(3) *Actions transform resources*

Let $m \in \mathbb{M}$. Recall the only case in δ that can construct such a node:

$$\delta(\langle m \rangle) = (\{m\}, \{\}, m, m, m_{in}, m_{out})$$

By Lemma 3, $F_{in}(m) = m_{in}$ and $F_{out}(m) = m_{out}$.

(4) *G is connected*

Trivially by Definition 15, for some action m , with $\delta(m) = (_, _, f, l, _, _)$, there is a path from f to l .

Additionally, in all other cases in δ , an inductive call to δ is made and there is a path from the first node of the outer call to the first node from the inner call, and a path from the last node of the inner call to the last node of the outer call.

By induction, the resulting graph is connected.

3 Conclusion

This report has provided a detailed formal account of the core constructs and transformations underlying the CLSP framework for synthesizing discrete-event simulation models. We introduced network terms as structured synthesis outputs and showed how they can be translated into consistent material flow graphs via graph expressions. The theoretical foundations ensure that every valid network term yields a valid simulation model structure, and that redundant or invalid configurations are systematically avoided.

By establishing a consistent mapping from logical synthesis terms to simulation-ready structures, this formalization lays the groundwork for scalable, automated generation of structural variants of simulation models. It is important to emphasize that the synthesis operates on the structural level and presupposes a domain-specific modeling framework with valid simulation actions. The method is not intended for the automatic generation of complete models of real-world systems.

This self-contained formal reference is meant to complement ongoing development work and support future research in component-based modeling, simulation synthesis, and logic-driven design space exploration. It is crucial to emphasize that the synthesis approach presented in this report builds upon a predefined modeling vocabulary and generates only structural variants of simulation model structures. It does not support the full automatic construction of valid simulation models for real-world systems. Instead, it contributes to design-space exploration by offering formally grounded mechanisms to systematically construct and compare structural alternatives within a validated modeling context.

4 Acknowledgement

This report was written as part of the project “KL4SiM – automated generation of structural variants for simulation models in the field of production and logistics using combinatorial logic”, funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) – 511349842.